

Psalm 84

"A and Ω"

For in truth it is so that
we are in timelessness.
Yet what cannot be overlooked
is that everything moves and changes.

But in reality it is so that, spiritually,
we can always remain focused
on one single point.

A place where all lines meet —

the face of Jesus Christ.

I stand before His countenance
and may behold Him like a brother.

And in Him and with Him
I also see thousands of faces
who lived in my bloodline before me.

And this is simply a
being opposite one another,
a beholding — an alliance.

Nothing more is required —
we are at peace.

Therefore, to me, nothing moves.
And at the same time,
everything moves around me.

And this is the higher equilibrium —
an image of the essence
of the Most High.

Perfectly unmoving — transcendent,

and

perfectly moving — immanent.

It is the A and the Ω in holy trinity.

(from the New Psalms — “The Way of the Open Heart”)